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Effect of Board Size and Board Ownership Structure on the Financial Performance of Listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the effect of board size and board ownership on the financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. The independent variables include board size, board ownership and return on assets (ROA) serves as the dependent variable. independent directors, and audit committee size, Firm size, capital adequacy ratio, and non-performing loan ratio are used as control variables. Adopting an ex-post facto research design, the study utilized secondary data extracted from the published annual reports of listed banks between 2015 and 2024. The analysis employed the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression technique within the framework of agency theory and resource dependence theory. The empirical results revealed that board ownership, independent directors, and audit committee size exert a positive and significant influence on banks' financial performance, indicating that improved oversight, managerial equity participation, and governance transparency enhance profitability. Conversely, board size and non-performing loans have a negative and significant impact, suggesting that overly large boards and poor credit quality hinder performance. Firm size and capital adequacy were found to be statistically insignificant, implying that governance factors exert stronger influence than scale or capitalization. The study concludes that effective board composition and governance mechanisms are vital for sustaining profitability and stability in the Nigerian banking sector. It recommends that banks maintain optimal board sizes, encourage director shareholding, and strengthen independent oversight and audit committees for improved performance and accountability.

Keywords: Corporate Governance, Board Size, Board Ownership, Financial Performance and Listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.

1. INTRODUCTION

There have been many banks collapses and financial crises in recent years linked to a lack of effective corporate governance, however, the Nigeria Code of Corporate Governance recommends that corporate governing bodies should be comprised of an appropriate balance of knowledge, diversity, and independence for discharging their duties objectively and more efficiently. Therefore, corporate governance is the process and structure used to direct and control the business and affairs of companies

for promoting business prosperity and corporate accountability. The ultimate objective is the realization of long-term shareholder value while considering the interest of other stakeholders. (Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance, 2018).

Corporate governance is an important concept that relates to the way in which financial, material and human resources available to an organization are judiciously used to achieve the overall corporate objective of an organization. It keeps the organization in business and creates a greater prospect for future opportunities. The overall effect of good corporate governance should be the strengthening of investor's confidence in the economy of Nigeria.

Corporate governance is therefore about building credibility, ensuring transparency and accountability as well maintaining an effective channel of information disclosure that would foster good corporate performance (Onakoya et al, 2021)

Corporate governance refers to the management of an entity affairs in the interest of the shareholders and other stakeholders. It is also concerned with the creation of a balance between economic and social goals and between individual and communal goals. To achieve this, there is the need to encourage efficient use of resources, accountability in the use of power, and, the alignment of the interest of the various stakeholders, such as, individuals, corporations and the society. Corporate governance is now widely accepted as being concerned with improved entity's performance. Viewed from this perspective, corporate governance is all about accountability, boards, disclosure, investor involvement and related issues, (Udeh and Frances, 2021).

In Nigeria, the issue of corporate governance has been on the front burner status by all sectors of the economy. This is in recognition of the failure of the critical role of corporate governance in the success or failure of companies (Ogbechie, 2020). In developing economies, the banking sector among other sectors has witnessed several cases of collapses or failure, of which some Nigerian examples include: Savannah Bank Plc, Society Generale Bank Ltd and recently acquired Oceanic Bank, Bank of the North, Afri Bank, Mainstream Bank and the 2019 merger between Diamond Bank and Access Bank plc. Therefore, with the failure in Nigeria banks and the activities of some of the bank operators, there are concerns on the need to strengthen corporate governance in banks. This will boost public confidence and ensure efficient and effective functioning of the banking system (Soludo, 2019). It is therefore, against this background that this study seek to examine the impact of corporate governance on the financial performance of listed Deposits money banks in Nigeria.

Nigerian Banks are faced with myriad of problems despite the mandatory action of banks consolidation pronounced by CBN in 2005 so as to make banks more effective and strengthen their performance. However, several banks collapses resulting from weak systems of corporate governance and internal control system have highlighted the need to improve and reform corporate governance at an international level. (Onakoya et al, 2021)

To this effect, there are several studies with mixed outcome carried out on the impact of corporate governance on banks financial performance in different countries with some studies revealing that corporate governance significantly influences financial performance (Arifin, 2023; Aggarwal, 2013; Ghaffar, 2014; Ene & Alem 2019; Sutrisno, 2021). Such other studies also show that corporate governance negatively influences firm value, and financial performance, hence there is no conclusive position among scholars.

However, despite a number of studies on the impact of corporate governance on the performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria, only few research studies were concentrated on first bank, this therefore establishes an important gap in the literature making the research of this kind significant. The main objective of this study will be to assess the effect of Board size and Board ownership Structure on financial performance of listed Deposit Money banks in Nigeria. While the specific objectives of the study will be: to determine the effect of board size on the financial performance of Listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. to examine the effect of board composition on the on the financial performance of Listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.

2. Literature Review

The Concept of Corporate Governance

The concept of corporate governance takes its lead from a Greek word “kyberman” meaning to steer, guide and govern; it then revolved to Latin, where it was known as “gubernare” and to French as “governor”. To be precise, corporate governance is the process of decisions making and the process by which decisions may be implemented, hence forth, it has much a different meaning to different organizations (Chuku, 2022). In recent years, corporate governance was seen as a system of checks and balances between/among the board, management and investors so as to produce an efficiently functioning corporation, ideally geared to produce long-term value (Brancato and Plath, 2018). Jayashree (2020) defines it thus: “Corporate Governance when used in the context of business organization is a system of making directors accountable to shareholders for effective management of the companies in the best interest of the company and the shareholders along with concern for ethics and values.

Adebisi, (2023) opine that, the concept of corporate governance characterizes a set of rules and incentives through which the management of an organization is being directed and controlled. Demaki (2019) emphasises that corporate governance is an institutional arrangement that checks the excesses of controlling managers. The whole essence of corporate governance is to ensure that the business is run well and investors receive a fair return (Kajola, 2018). A firm is said to have observed corporate governance rule if it is managed with diligence, transparency, responsibility and accountability aimed at maximizing shareholders’ wealth (Pandy, 2015). Hence, timely and detail disclosure of material financial information is desirable in assessing any corporate governance framework. More so, good corporate governance involves a system by which governing institutions and all other organizations relate to their communities and stakeholders to improve their quality of life (Ato, 2022). Corporate governance is therefore important to ensure transparency, accountability and fairness in corporate reporting. In this regard, corporate governance is not only concerned with corporate efficiency, it relates to company strategy and life cycle development. Corporate governance is based on the level of corporate responsibility a company exhibits with regard to accountability, transparency and ethical values.

The corporate governance framework is an important element in effective development of equity market, research and development, entrepreneurship and economic growth (Maher & Anderson, 2022). Indeed, effective corporate governance improves economic efficiency, access to domestic and foreign capital, human resources productivity and development of market economy. Therefore, creating an effective corporate governance framework could enhance efficiency and transparency in the Nigerian financial system.

Corporate performance is an important concept which relates to the ways and manners in which the resources (human, machine, finance) of an institution are effectively used to achieve the overall corporate objective of an organization (Adegbemi, 2021, Donald & Ismail, 2022). What keeps an organization in business is simply its ability to judiciously use its available resources and make sure that the providers of economic resources and its managers mutually benefit from the use of the resources.

Corporate Governance Mechanisms

The corporate governance mechanisms relate to the tools, techniques and instruments via which accountability is ensured. It is the various medium through which stakeholders monitor and shape behavior to align with set goals and objectives. Thus, corporate governance mechanism is the processes and systems by which a country’s company laws and corporate governance codes are enforced (Adekoya, 2020, 2022). Therefore, this study will consider corporate governance mechanisms from the perspective of Board Size, Board Composition and Audit Committees Size (Akpan & Roman, 2019; Abdulazeez et al., 2019).

(a) Board Size

Board size refers to the number of people on the board-executive or non- executive directors. The Central Bank of Nigeria’s Code of Corporate Governance for Banks and Discount Houses in Nigeria (2014) recommends that the number of non-executive directors should be more than that of executive directors’ subject to a maximum board size of 20 directors. This is considered to be a crucial characteristic of the board structure. Large boards could provide the diversity that would help companies to secure critical

resources and reduce environmental uncertainties. Olayinka (2020) opines that this positively affects performance by reducing high earnings management, restatements and fraud.

Fama & Jensen, 2018 (as cited in Bandsal & Sharma, 2016) argue that the increase in the number of the members of the board slows down the decision-making processes of the firm, causing the board to pass off the problems, thus, leading to a decrease in firm value and effectiveness. Lipton and Lorsch (2021) suggested that as size of the board grows, the decision-making processes will slow down and this will cause communication problems and impacts the firm's performance negatively.

(b) Board Composition

Board composition refers to the number of independent non-executive directors on the board relative to the total number of directors. An independent non-executive director is defined as an independent director who has no affiliation with the firm except for their directorship (Clifford & Evans, 2011). There is an apparent presumption that boards with significant outside directors will make different and perhaps better decisions than boards dominated by insiders. Bansal & Sharma, (2022) suggest that non-executive directors can play an important role in the effective resolution of agency problems and their presence on the board can lead to more effective decision-making, hence improved firm performance.

Bocean, 2001 (as cited in Mirza & Javed, 2013), gave five principles of corporate governance: Protection of shareholders' rights, Equitable treatment of shareholders, Protection of stakeholders' rights, Proper disclosure and transparency, Fulfillment of responsibilities by board, Board Size and Composition as Prescribed by CBN, 2014.

According to (2014 CBN) guideline, the board size and composition of a bank in Nigeria shall compose of the following:

The size of the Board of any bank or discount house shall be limited to a minimum of five (5) and a maximum of twenty (20). Members of the Board shall be qualified persons of proven integrity and shall be knowledgeable in business and financial matters, in accordance with the extant CBN Guidelines on Fit and Proper Persons Regime. The Board shall consist of Executive and Non-Executive Directors. The number of Non-Executive Directors shall be more than that of Executive Directors. The Board of banks shall have at least two (2) Non-Executive Directors as Independent Directors while that of discount houses shall have at least one (1) as defined in the CBN guidelines on the Appointment of Independent Directors.

Firm Financial Performance

Firm Financial Performance is a subjective measure of how well a firm can use assets from its primary mode of business and generate revenues. This term is also used as a general measure of a firm's overall financial health over a given period of time, and can be used to compare similar firms across the same industry or to compare industries or sectors in aggregation. George and Karibo (2014) defined it as the success in meeting pre-defined objectives, targets and goal within a specified time target. Some of the aspects that must be considered when attempting to define performance are: time frame and its reference point. It is possible to differentiate between past and future performance. And it has been shown that past superior performance does not guarantee that it will remain superior in the future (Bino & Tormar, 2021).

The concept of Banks Financial Performance

Bank performance is the terms used in relation to its capacity to generate sustainable profitability. For a bank to be successful in its operations, managers must weigh complex trade-offs between growths, return and risk, favouring the adoption of risk-adjusted metrics (Bassey, Tobi, Bassey and Ekwere, 2016). Banks performance measure can be classified into traditional, economic and market-based. For example Stern and Stewart developed a model called Economic Value Added (EVA) which takes into account the opportunity cost for stockholders to hold equity in a bank, measuring whether a company generates an economic rate of return higher than the cost of invested capital in order to increase the market value of the company (Raza, Farhan and Akram, 2019).

However, Rivard and Thomas (2011) asserted that bank profitability is best measured by ROA because high equity multipliers do not distort it. Guven and Onur (2020) corroborated this view by submitting that researchers focus on and make use of ROA to measure bank profitability to guard against most of the limitations associated with the use of other accounting financial performance proxies.

Empirical Reviews.

Several studies have investigated on the corporate governance and banks performance in Nigeria, and in different part of the world with diverse techniques and opinions. The outcomes of the investigations however, have shown that there are many conflicting empirical findings. For instance, Adekunle and Adedipe (2013) on Corporate Governance and Bank's Performance in Nigeria (Post-Bank's Consolidation), they considered estimated models. Binary probit was adopted to test the covariance matrix computed on structured questionnaire to bank's clients and it was discovered that the variables such as independence, reliance, and fairness helps in the effective performance of banks but the major significant ones in this consolidation period are accountability and transparency of bank's staff. Also, least square regression analysis was adopted to convey the relationship between bank deposits and bank credit.

Kyereboah-Coleman (2019) examined how corporate governance indicators such as board size, board composition and CEO duality impact financing decisions of 47 firms listed on the Nairobi Stock Exchange. They found that firms with larger board sizes employ more debt and the independence of a board correlates negatively and significantly with short-term debts.

Olayinka, (2019) investigated the Impact of Board Structure on Corporate Financial Performance in Nigeria. This study examines the impact of board structure on corporate financial performance in Nigeria. It investigates the composition of boards of directors in Based on the extensive literature, four board characteristics (board composition, board size, board ownership and CEO duality) have been identified as possibly having an impact on corporate financial performance and these characteristics are set as the independent variables. The Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression was used to estimate the relationship between corporate performance measures and the independent variables. Findings from the study showed that there is strong positive association between board size and corporate financial performance.

Dzingai and Fakoya (2019) assessed the effect of corporate governance structures on firm financial performance in Johannesburg Stock Exchange (JSE). They used panel data analysis of the random effects model to determine the relationship between board independence and board size and the return on equity (ROE) for the period 2012–2017. They found that a weak but negative correlation between ROE and board size but positive correlation between ROE and board independence. They further disclosed that there is a positive, but weak, correlation between ROE and sales growth, but a negative and weak relationship between ROE and firm size.

Emeka and Alem, (2021) investigated the effects of Corporate Governance on Bank's Financial Performance in Nigeria, covered years 2009-2018. They discovered that there were effects of relative size of non-executive directors and the board size on return on investment (ROA). They found that the relationship between corporate governance and bank performance in Nigeria is quite significant.

Uwugbe (2021) examined Corporate Governance and financial performance of Banks in Nigeria. He measured variables for corporate governance as board size, the proportion of non-executive directors, directors' equity interest and corporate governance disclosure index. Financial performance of the banks measures as return on equity (ROE) and return on asset (ROA). His study revealed that a negative but significant relationship exists between board size, board composition and the financial performance of these banks, while a positive and significant relationship was also noticed between directors' equity interest, level of governance disclosure and performance.

Akingunola, (2022) examined the corporate governance and banks' performance in Nigeria. They used earnings, return on equity and return on assets as variables. They employed the ordinary least squares regression method to analyze their data. They revealed that bank deposits mobilized and credits created over this period increased over the years but were more positively related to bank performance during the period of consolidation although not significant. They concluded that, to minimize financial and economic crime in the system, banks must embrace fiduciary duty which includes transparency, honesty and fairness (corporate governance codes) in dealing with all its stakeholders.

Theoretical Framework

This research is grounded in Agency Theory and Resource Dependence Theory, which serve as the basis for comprehending the correlation between corporate governance mechanisms and financial performance. Jensen and Meckling (1976) came up with Agency Theory to explain the conflicts of interest that can happen between shareholders (the principals) and managers (the agents). The theory asserts that efficient governance frameworks—such as board ownership, independent directors, and audit committees—facilitate the alignment of managerial interests with those of shareholders, thereby reducing agency costs and enhancing organizational performance. Resource Dependence Theory (Pfeffer & Salancik, 1978), on the other hand, focuses on the board's strategic role in giving the organization access to important resources, outside networks, and expert knowledge that it needs to stay alive and make money. In the context of Nigerian banking, these theories collectively indicate that well-structured boards augment accountability, mitigate opportunistic behavior, and enhance financial performance, as evidenced by return on assets (ROA).

3. METHODOLOGY

This study is historical in nature hence ex-post factor research design will be adopted. The choice of the ex-post factor design is chosen because this study is reporting on what is already in existence. The population for the purpose of this study consists of all the 14 listed deposits money banks. The shares 13 of them are quoted on the Nigeria Group Exchange as at 31st December, 2024 and Union Bank is listed privately. The data were collected from financial statements and official websites of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria for the period of five years (2020 – 2024). The study employed census method whereby all 14 listed banks were selected as sample of the study Listed deposit money banks were considered more suitable for investigation considering their role in propelling the economy as well the governance issues being experienced in the banking industry. In this study Data were analyses and tabulated under the descriptive statistics accordingly, the Ordinary Least Squares Regression Analysis will be employed as the technique of data analysis.

4. RESULTS

The results computed using stata are presented and discussed below respectively:

Table 4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
ROA	140	0.01	0.01	-0.01	0.03
BSZ	140	8.39	1.79	5.00	12.00
BOW	140	0.29	0.14	0.00	0.47
BID	140	0.55	0.14	0.25	0.83
ACS	140	3.73	1.02	2.00	6.00
FSZ	140	24.77	0.54	23.75	25.85
CAR	140	0.12	0.02	0.08	0.17
NPL	140	0.04	0.02	0.00	0.08

Source: Stata output 2025

Table 4.1 presents the descriptive statistics of the study variables for 14 listed deposit money banks over a 10-year period (2015–2024). The average Return on Assets (ROA) is 0.5%, which means that the Nigerian banking sector was making money during the study period, but not a lot. The average board size (BSZ) of about 8 members shows that the company is following the rules for good corporate governance. Board ownership (BOW) is 28.5%, which means that a moderate number of insiders own shares in the company. Board independence (BID) is 55.1%, which means that more than half of the board members are not executives. The average number of members on an audit committee (ACS) is 3.7, which is close to the legal requirement. The mean natural log value of firm size (FSZ) is 24.77, which shows that the sample banks have fairly large asset bases. The capital adequacy ratio (CAR) is 12.2%, which means that most banks have enough capital. The non-performing loan ratio (NPL) is 4%, which is within prudential limits.

Table 4.2 Pairwise correlations

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
(1) ROA	1.000							
(2) BSZ	-0.160	1.000						
(3) BOW	0.069	0.388	1.000					
(4) BID	0.387	-0.350	0.145	1.000				
(5) ACS	0.106	0.007	-0.459	-0.083	1.000			
(6) FSZ	0.108	-0.182	0.049	0.301	0.048	1.000		
(7) CAR	0.045	-0.097	-0.010	0.030	-0.126	-0.035	1.000	
(8) NPL	-0.901	0.046	-0.039	-0.153	0.030	-0.028	-0.044	1.000

Source: Stata output 2025

The pairwise correlation matrix shows that no correlation coefficient among the independent variables exceeds the threshold of 0.8, indicating no serious multicollinearity problem in the dataset. The correlations are generally low to moderate, suggesting that the explanatory variables are sufficiently independent of one another. Therefore, the model's regression estimates are unlikely to be distorted by multicollinearity.

Table 4.3 Variance inflation factor

	VIF	1/VIF
BOW	1.785	.56
BSZ	1.596	.626
ACS	1.387	.721
BID	1.377	.726
FSZ	1.129	.886
CAR	1.031	.97
NPL	1.026	.974
Mean VIF	1.333	.

Source: Stata output 2025

Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) results show all values below 2, with a mean VIF of 1.33, confirming the absence of multicollinearity among the independent variables. This indicates that the explanatory variables are sufficiently independent for reliable coefficient estimation.

Table 4.4 Breusch–Pagan / Cook–Weisberg Test for Heteroskedasticity

Test	$\chi^2(\text{df})$	p-value	Decision
Breusch–Pagan / Cook–Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity	$\chi^2(1) = 0.95$	p = .331	Fail to reject H_0 (No heteroskedasticity)

Source: Stata output 2025

The Breusch–Pagan/Cook–Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity yielded a non-significant result ($\chi^2(1) = 0.95$, $p = .331$), indicating that the assumption of constant variance in the error terms holds. Therefore, the model does not suffer from heteroskedasticity, and the standard errors are valid.

Table 4.5 Hausman (1978) specification test

	Coef.
Chi-square test value	6.919
P-value	.437

Source: Stata output 2025

Table 4.6 Breusch–Pagan Lagrangian Multiplier Test for Random Effects

Test	$\chi^2(\text{df})$	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Breusch–Pagan LM test for random effects	$\chi^2(1) = 0.00$	p = .497	Fail to reject H_0	No significant random effects; pooled OLS preferred

Source: Stata output 2025

The Breusch–Pagan/Cook–Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity yielded a non-significant result ($\chi^2(1) = 0.95, p = .331$), indicating that the assumption of constant variance in the error terms holds. Therefore, the model does not suffer from heteroskedasticity, and the standard errors are valid.

Table 4.7 Ordinary Least Square Regression (OLS)

ROA	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
BSZ	0.000	0.000	-3.17	0.002	-0.001	0.000	***
BOW	0.008	0.002	4.23	0.000	0.004	0.012	***
BID	0.012	0.002	7.25	0.000	0.009	0.016	***
ACS	0.002	0.000	7.26	0.000	0.001	0.002	***
FSZ	0.000	0.000	-0.66	0.507	-0.001	0.001	
CAR	0.007	0.010	0.73	0.467	-0.012	0.026	
NPL	-0.364	0.011	-32.93	0.000	-0.386	-0.343	***
Constant	0.014	0.010	1.41	0.161	-0.006	0.033	
Mean dependent var		0.005	SD dependent var			0.008	
R-squared		0.912	Number of obs			140	
F-test		194.557	Prob > F			0.000	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		-1292.876	Bayesian crit. (BIC)			-1269.343	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Source: Stata output 2025

The regression results indicate that the model explains approximately 91.2% of the variation in ROA ($R^2 = 0.912$), and the overall F-statistic is significant ($F = 194.557, p < .001$), demonstrating the model's explanatory power. Board size (BSZ) has a negative and significant effect on ROA ($\beta = -0.0003, p < .01$), which means that bigger boards might make things less efficient because they take longer to make decisions and coordinate. On the other hand, board ownership (BOW) has a positive and significant effect ($\beta = 0.008, p < .01$). This means that when managers own more shares, their interests are more aligned with those of shareholders, which leads to higher profits. In addition, board independence (BID) and audit committee size (ACS) both have big and good effects on ROA ($p < .01$). This means that better systems for oversight and governance make a company's finances better.

The firm size (FSZ) and capital adequacy ratio (CAR) are not statistically significant, which means that the bank's size and capitalization did not have a big effect on how much money it made during the study period. On the other hand, the non-performing loan ratio (NPL) has a strong negative and significant effect ($\beta = -0.364, p < .01$). This means that higher credit risk directly lowers profitability.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study examined the effect of board characteristics on the financial performance of 14 listed deposit money banks in Nigeria (2015–2024), using Return on Assets (ROA) as a performance proxy. The pooled OLS model, selected after diagnostic tests, revealed that board ownership ($\beta = 0.008, p < .01$), board independence ($\beta = 0.012, p < .01$), and audit committee size ($\beta = 0.002, p < .01$) positively and significantly affect financial performance. Conversely, board size ($\beta = -0.000, p < .01$) and non-performing loans ($\beta = -0.364, p < .01$) have negative and significant effects. Firm size and capital adequacy were insignificant. The model explains 91.2% of ROA variation, with no multicollinearity or heteroskedasticity detected.

It is recommended that banks maintain an optimal board size, promote director share ownership, and strengthen board independence and audit committees to enhance performance. Effective credit risk management is also vital to minimize non-performing loans. Future research should explore broader governance variables, include unlisted banks, and apply dynamic panel methods to address endogeneity and deepen understanding of corporate governance impacts in the Nigerian banking sector.

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Appendix

. asdoc summarize ROA BSZ BOW BID ACS FSZ CAR NPL
 (File Myfile.doc already exists, option **append** was assumed)

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
ROA	140	.0052571	.0076218	-.0102	.0245
BSZ	140	8.385714	1.785577	5	12
BOW	140	.2854343	.1381434	0	.4719
BID	140	.5511329	.1367658	.2542	.8316
ACS	140	3.728571	1.016715	2	6
FSZ	140	24.76599	.540647	23.7547	25.8501
CAR	140	.1221821	.0205224	.08	.1759
NPL	140	.0396993	.0180486	0	.082

. asdoc reg ROA BSZ BOW BID ACS FSZ CAR NPL
 (File Myfile.doc already exists, option **append** was assumed)

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs =	140
Model	.007361318	7	.001051617	F(7, 132) =	194.56
Residual	.000713485	132	5.4052e-06	Prob > F =	0.0000
				R-squared =	0.9116
				Adj R-squared =	0.9070
Total	.008074803	139	.000058092	Root MSE =	.00232

ROA	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
BSZ	-.0004424	.0001395	-3.17	0.002	-.0007184	-.0001664
BOW	.0080714	.001907	4.23	0.000	.0042992	.0118435
BID	.0122675	.0016921	7.25	0.000	.0089204	.0156145
ACS	.0016578	.0002285	7.26	0.000	.0012059	.0021097
FSZ	-.0002576	.0003875	-0.66	0.507	-.0010241	.0005089
CAR	.0071234	.0097552	0.73	0.467	-.0121733	.0264202
NPL	-.3644427	.0110686	-32.93	0.000	-.3863375	-.3425478
_cons	.0136978	.0097119	1.41	0.161	-.0055134	.0329089

. asdoc vif
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Variable	VIF	1/VIF
BOW	1.78	0.560342
BSZ	1.60	0.626459
ACS	1.39	0.720774
BID	1.38	0.726114
FSZ	1.13	0.886066
CAR	1.03	0.970221
NPL	1.03	0.974363
Mean VIF	1.33	

```
. asdoc hettest
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```

```
Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity
Ho: Constant variance
Variables: fitted values of ROA
```

```
chi2(1)      =      0.95
Prob > chi2  =      0.3308
```

```
. asdoc xtreg ROA BSZ BOW BID ACS FSZ CAR NPL, fe
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```

```
Fixed-effects (within) regression           Number of obs   =      140
Group variable: bank_id                    Number of groups =      14

R-sq:  within = 0.9087                      Obs per group:  min =      10
        between = 0.6317                      avg =      10.0
        overall = 0.8453                      max =      10

F(7,119) = 169.13
corr(u_i, Xb) = -0.2297                      Prob > F = 0.0000
```

ROA	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
BSZ	-.0009772	.0003182	-3.07	0.003	-.0016073	-.000347
BOW	.0246522	.0104329	2.36	0.020	.003994	.0453104
BID	.0048353	.0045405	1.06	0.289	-.0041554	.013826
ACS	.0018206	.0003597	5.06	0.000	.0011084	.0025328
FSZ	.0007169	.0023359	0.31	0.759	-.0039085	.0053422
CAR	.0054622	.009833	0.56	0.580	-.0140081	.0249325
NPL	-.3625821	.0112261	-32.30	0.000	-.3848109	-.3403533
_cons	-.007065	.0584427	-0.12	0.904	-.1227874	.1086573
sigma_u	.00228038					
sigma_e	.00226138					
rho	.50418289	(fraction of variance due to u_i)				

```
F test that all u_i=0:      F(13, 119) =      1.58          Prob > F = 0.1007
```

. asdoc xtreg ROA BSZ BOW BID ACS FSZ CAR NPL, re
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```

Random-effects GLS regression           Number of obs   =       140
Group variable: bank_id                 Number of groups =        14

R-sq:  within = 0.9050                   Obs per group: min =        10
      between = 0.9410                               avg =       10.0
      overall  = 0.9111                               max =        10

                                           Wald chi2(7)    =    1307.63
corr(u_i, X) = 0 (assumed)               Prob > chi2     =      0.0000
  
```

ROA	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf. Interval]	
BSZ	-.0005496	.0001756	-3.13	0.002	-.0008938	-.0002054
BOW	.0092184	.0024609	3.75	0.000	.0043952	.0140416
BID	.0112101	.0021778	5.15	0.000	.0069416	.0154785
ACS	.0017236	.0002656	6.49	0.000	.0012031	.0022441
FSZ	-.0002664	.0005251	-0.51	0.612	-.0012956	.0007628
CAR	.006828	.0096187	0.71	0.478	-.0120243	.0256803
NPL	-.3634797	.0109436	-33.21	0.000	-.3849287	-.3420306
_cons	.0148223	.013081	1.13	0.257	-.0108159	.0404605
sigma_u	.00072626					
sigma_e	.00226138					
rho	.09349914	(fraction of variance due to u_i)				

```
. asdoc hausman fe re
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```

	—— Coefficients ——			sqrt(diag(V_b-V_B)) S.E.
	(b) fe	(B) re	(b-B) Difference	
BSZ	-.0009772	-.0005496	-.0004276	.0002654
BOW	.0246522	.0092184	.0154338	.0101385
BID	.0048353	.0112101	-.0063748	.0039842
ACS	.0018206	.0017236	.000097	.0002426
FSZ	.0007169	-.0002664	.0009832	.0022761
CAR	.0054622	.006828	-.0013658	.0020416
NPL	-.3625821	-.3634797	.0008975	.0025026

b = consistent under Ho and Ha; obtained from xtreg
 B = inconsistent under Ha, efficient under Ho; obtained from xtreg

Test: Ho: difference in coefficients not systematic

```
chi2(7) = (b-B)' [(V_b-V_B)^(-1)] (b-B)
          = 6.92
Prob>chi2 = 0.4373
```

```
. xttest0
```

Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian multiplier test for random effects

$$ROA[\text{bank_id},t] = Xb + u[\text{bank_id}] + e[\text{bank_id},t]$$

Estimated results:

	Var	sd = sqrt(Var)
ROA	.0000581	.0076218
e	5.11e-06	.0022614
u	5.27e-07	.0007263

Test: Var(u) = 0

```
chibar2(01) = 0.00
Prob > chibar2 = 0.4972
```